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GAL : A Little Explore But Crucial Question of Quest for Just Regulation pf Expanding Powerful Global Entities in The Age of Global Governance

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Abstract

It is common accusation of certain developing and under-developed countries that in the modern global order there emerged many powerful global bodies which abuse their capacity to regulate the their sovereign subjects including the private people, and said organisations often found biased to serve the vested interests of powerful developed countries. Whereas jurists and thinkers pertaining to the field of international law, accept the fact that a global governing administration is taking shape through these powerful global bodies where it is the *defacto* phenomenon of rising real and virtual global connectivity among the people. These pressed that there is need to develop Global Administrative law to enhance acceptability of global bodies by ensuring their proper regulation on democratic equitable values. Thus it is accepted fact that these nascent global institutions started driving a neo-global state, but unfortunately there credibility is on stake owing to complaint that powerful capitalist economies of western world influence the shaping of policies and agendas by these global institutions, resultantly putting vulnerable societies and poor countries at a disadvantageous position. At the same time the proposed mechanism of GAL is facing many issuing as to its possible sources, subjects, nature, models and structure

Keywords GAL, ICT, Global organisations, Global State.

Introduction

One can't deny the fact that the modern day-light have witnesses ancient dream of the human-race to bring entire globe closer like a village called "*Vasudhaiva Kutumbkam*" as reality, thanks to technological advancements of novel mediums of transport and communication. It has ensured an unprecedented proximity to the interaction and connectivity among the people around every corner of the globe, as nowadays the classical barriers created under economic-political set-up of nation-states have been diluted to a large extent, and the ideas of 'entire globe one country' and 'global village' becomes a reality. The phenomenon of globalisation has touched almost each sphere of human life activity, as dimension of human activity has been remained immune/exception from world level regulation. (1) The fast pace of connectivity at every corner of globe enhance transaction at every sort, thus to regulate the growing transactions and interactions at global level among states and their citizens, many global institutions, networks, organisations, unions have been established, such as WTO, WB IMF etcetera. These global bodies undisputedly have influence and authority to affect the very sovereign space of classical nation-states and life of the its citizens, when they take administrative decisions or actions, affecting any political, economic, cultural or social stake of any sovereign state or its citizens.(2) However the question that it is with the active consent of such classical nation-states or not, matter the least, as it's a phenomenal fact, which one

can easily perceive. On this world phenomenal reality, the crucial question perplexed the thinkers and scholars of international law is that, there is always scope of abuse authority in arbitrary way by these institution's administration under the undue-influence of powerful nations, to further their vested interests. (3) 'Power corrupts and absolute power corrupts absolutely'(4) is a famous saying in the field of administrative law, for just working of domestic municipal nation-states', administrative law has been developed in every civilised state. On Same line need is felt in the arena of global sphere

Objective of study

To study the phenomenal existence and impact of Global Administrative state viz-a-viz Global Bodies. 2. To Analyse the need to regulate the global organistion and bodies. 3. Analysis the impact of neo-global world phenomenon on weak countries. 4. Critical Anaylsis of issues and challneges in deveopment of GAL and its functioning. 5. To discuss the tentative shape of GAL as an effective and adequate mechanism to regulate the global governance.

Review of Literature

For the research article "**GAL : A little explored, but crucial question of quest for just regulation of expanding powerful global entities in the age of global governance**" following literature is thoroughly perused and studied by the researcher.

Dr. Devinder Singh in , "**An Introduction to The Administrative Law**", hold that the people at every corner of globe enhance transaction at every sort, and to regulate the growing transactions and interactions at global level among states and their citizens, many global institutions, networks, organisations, unions have been established that affect the very sovereign space of states and life of the its citizens, when they take administrative decisions or actions, affecting any political, economic, cultural or social stake of any sovereign state or its citizens. (5)

Rajeshwar Tripathi in "**Concept of Global Administrative Law :An Overview**" hold that, Globalisation has integrated the entire world into a unit with a vast range of regulatory regime, and has led to the emergence of a neo-global state through international institutions. These global institutions directly or indirectly regulate the social, economic and political functions of states. In this way GAL is related to trans-governmental regulation and administration designed to address the consequences of globalised interdependence in such fields. This phenomenon has led to the question of accountability, fairness and transparency and due process in the functioning of these global administrative bodies. [6]

B.S. Chimni in the paper "**Co-option and Resistance: Two Faces of Global Administrative Law**" critiques the Global Administrative Law (GAL) initiative from a third world perspective. He argues that, in the absence of a simultaneous reform of substantive law, GAL has only limited potential to contribute to justice in the international system, and even may legitimize unjust laws and institutions. Modern global institutions are not, for the most part, being made more participatory and responsive to the concerns of developing countries and its peoples. Thus, GAL can play a vital role as an instrument of resistance and change. [7]

Benedict Kingsbury, Nico Krisch & Richard B. Stewart in the article "**The Emergence of Global Administrative Law**" expressed their views thatemerging patterns of global governance are being shaped by a little-noticed but important and growing body of GAL. This body of law is not at present unified indeed, it is not yet an organized field of scholarship or of practice. [8]

Sabino Cassese, Bruno Carotti, Lorenzo Casini, Eleonora Cavalieri & Euan MacDonald (editors) in their book, "**Global Administrative Law: The Casebook**" have made an attempt to analyse global administrative law through the elaboration and examination of a number of different cases and case-studies. They tried to put light on the broader governance context in which global governance is situated. [9]

Carol Harlow in, " Global Administrative Law: The Quest For Principles and Values", examine the proposed shape of GAL along with probable challneges and constraints with issues. (10)

Benedict Kingsbury in the article “**Weighing Global Regulatory Rules and Decisions in National Courts**” opined that Global regulatory governance is increasingly conducted by extra-national/global institutions by adopting administrative-style rules and regulations, or specific decisions concerning individual entities, which affect private actors or state agencies in ways that eventually come to be considered in national courts. This global regulatory governance produces unfamiliar challenges for national courts. [11]

Main Text

The contemporary global institutions have an imperial character and a global capitalist class (corporate lobby) has emerged, which influence formation of international laws and global organisation to further their vested corporate interest. (12) As discussed above the enhanced transaction and connectivity at global level make the scholars to think to ensure proper mechanisms to well regulate the growing interactions at global level.(13) This assumption about the global bodies is based on a study of recent developments in global laws relating to the use of force, trans-national migration, global media laws and refugee laws. These developments resultantly give rise to an unequal world order in which the north-south divide continues to grow, whereas developing Asian-African societies are allegedly put at disadvantage, whereas powerful states of west are less constrained in the use of force against third world states and developing economies. (14)

Here it is relevant to discuss that administrative law is the body of those fine rules based mechanisms, which are meant to well regulate the administration in order to rule out chances of misuse of authority in arbitrary and unjust manner.(15) In modern welfare states, an advanced administrative law has been evolved, for the same. On same lines, the notion of GAL take birth from the two ideas that global governance with emerging global bodies can be understood as administration, that should be organised and structured by principles having an administrative law character.(16) Many scholars prominent in International law argued for ensuring due regulation of these global bodies with proposal of GAL. In GAL they proposed to unite/integrate the structure of rules and principles through which subjects affected by these global bodies can be better governed. (17) They argue that on the lines of administrative law, certain minimum principles and procedures of natural justice, good governance and equity should be evolved, settled and adopted within the global institutions.(18) As per them the emerging global state, required a just, democratic and comprehensive global administrative law.(19) But distinction can be discerned in GAL, from domestic administration law on the ground that regulation of global bodies is different in its nature and scope from domestic administration. (20)

Here GAL is proposed to be a nascent structure at evolving state, with combination of international regulation and administrative law. At global level, lack of uniformity, certainty and concreteness in the international law is the reason for dearth of democratic spirit in global bodies. Thus, unlike the domestic administrative law, where adherence to certain uniform or just principles, while taking administrative action by executives, can be discerned, in global regulatory body such certainty and uniformity is missing. Instances of biasness by these global regulatory entities in favour of powerful developed nation at the loss of third world countries are not uncommon. Even the very scope/ jurisdiction/domain of such global bodies is not clear, though their presence into domestic sovereign affairs is marking an unprecedented phenomenon. Thus, uniform adherence of certain administrative principles by global bodies with clarity about their jurisdiction and subjects has been desired, to prevent exploitation of weak states and its citizens to ensure smooth functioning of global transactions and enhance faith in such institutions and bodies.

Definition/Meaning of GAL

GAL is claimed to be an evolving branch of administrative law, meant to regulate global institutions and international law. It is not easy to define the evolving concept of GAL in any precise or settled terms. Even the very concept of global governance is challenged to be based on an amorphous notion, by presenting the logic that, global governance intended to provide global governance akin to concept of domestic administration of a country, does not have that feasibility. (21) Thus, the definition of GAL is still a highly challenging task as its relations with international law, municipal/state regulation and constitutional law are not yet settled. (22) Yet some scholars have attempted to define it, by explaining its nature, scope and essential characteristics while picking some of the globally recognised principles of international law and civilised nations with some of

necessary objectives which GAL should intended to achieve. (23) The concept of international administrative law (*internationales Verwaltungsrecht*) has been originally coined by Lorenz Von Stein, in 1866 while describing it as an collection of legal rules partially based on international sources and to an extent dependent domestic sources dealing with administrative activity in the international field as a whole.(24) Kingsbury defined it as a set-up comprising the mechanisms, principles, practices and social understandings to promote the accountability of global administrative bodies, particularly by ensuring that it would meet adequate standards of transparency, good governance, participation, reasoned decisions and legality and effective review.(25) GAL is the adoption of some administrative law character principles, evolved or recognised within civilised states having an advanced democratic governance system, to global governance. Therefore, GAL is drawn on legal principles and practices prevalent in many domestic and regional legal systems and traditions, while picked as per suitability from sources in international Law.(26) The idea of the emerging global administrative law is animated by the view that much of global governance, especially global regulatory governance by global organisations, can be analysed as administration.(27) Instead of strictly separated levels of regulation GAL is a combination of many actors with different layers of integrated 'global administrative space' (28) Thus, the very idea of a 'global administrative space' marks a departure from those conservative classical understandings of international law in which the international is inter-governmental.(29) To avoid this technical confusion it is described as 'global' rather than 'international' in order to accomodate informal institutional arrangements and other normative practices, that are not encompassed within standard conceptions of 'international law'.(30) Further as per many modern jurists, GAL is neither only global, nor limited to administration, nor works mere as a law. It is not only global, as includes many trans-national, supranational, regional or local agreements and authorities.(31) Global administrative law also includes many types of soft law and standards, like directions, resolutions and commitments.(32)

Subjects under GAL

Traditionally, the subjects of International law are states, but now this dimension has taken a paradigm shift, as regulatory programs agreed to at the global level by states, are effectuated through measures taken by governments at the domestic level to regulate private conduct. (33) In many cases ultimately private actors are formally addressed only at the implementation/execution stage by the national administration. This characterisation is very powerful when these global bodies take decisions that have direct legal consequences for private individuals, as in case of Resolution of Security Council restricting/regulating trade, United Nation High Commission (UNHCR) for Refugees determinations of individuals' refugee status. (34) Similarly the adherence of TRIPS agreement qua regulating IPRs by all nations have impact on the choice of individual's activity as to manufacture, produce and create. Even the change in Indian personal laws is influenced by global cultural organisations. The aim of the nascent global regime is to achieve desired changes/reforms in private conduct along with state conduct. Thus, this novel expanding horizon of global organisations indicates that many important sovereign regulatory functions are no longer remain just domestic in character. (35) This is even true in the area of rule-making in which international action combine with action by national regulators in networks of global co-ordination to supplement or even determine domestic regulatory programmes and decisions. (36) Thus the subjects of GAL also travel along with scope, influence and area of the working of Global bodies.

Source of GAL

As discussed above Global Administrative is being multi-layered and diverse in nature, include very comprehensive and broad sources. These sources of GAL include the modern rules and regulations of international organisations along with the classical sources of public international law, such as includes treaties, custom and general principles.(37) The said sources provide jurisprudential material, comparative procedural and normative rules to provide the scope for the formation of GAL. Recognised treaties, settled international customs, prevalent general principle of laws accepted in civilised nations, domestic legislations and rules of global organisations are best sources to evolve/develop GAL. Treaty can addresses the issues of administrative functioning by spelling out principles of administrative procedure and substantive rights, whereas the customary international law, can provides the scope of GAL, inform to fairness and transparency. (38) Further the use of general principles of law including *Res Judicata*, *Estoppel*, *audi alterem partem*, *Restitution*, *review* helps the development of procedural

rules for the GAL. Municipal legislations by states related to administration like RTI and CCS rules can always proved a good source of GAL. Global Institutions are also one of best the sources of GAL when they adopted internal mechanisms for participation and Accountability such as ombudsman.

Nature and Characteristics of GAL

GAL is the body of law or law-like principles governing the procedural dimensions of an increasingly important global administrative space. As a field of theoretical scholarship, in study of GAL, much attention is given on the set-up of global governance institutions/organisations and their interactions with one-another and other private/extrnational.(39) Further, the methodology of GAL is focused on identifying global administration and, through an inductive method, developing procedural and proscriptive rules/norms.(40) Some neo-jurists define GAL as an administrative law based concept comprising of mechanisms, rules, values, supporting social understandings that ensure the accountability of global administrative bodies.(41) Administrative law at domestic level, is shaped as per the nature, character, *grund-norm* and stage of civilisation of the respected state-cum-society as in a liberal democratic states is more consistent to the egalitarian democratic principles. Needless to say that to understand the working of administrative law in a particular state, it is required to study the ideology, policy and setup of the concerned state. GAL can assume different shapes and nature depending on the nature and character of the concerned institutions. So, to prior to selecting a particular mode of GAL, it is must to understand the nature of particular global Organisations.(42) As administrative Law, GAL is also iprovides such rules and principles which ensure that the global administrative authorities must adhere to the rule of law in their function. In this respect, GAL may be described as a specific branch of public law that, examining the legal phenomena, which alsoconstitute global administration, seeks to discover and specify the norms that govern this administration and to supplement them. Thus, GAL covers all the rules and procedures that help to ensure the accountability of global administration, and it focuses in particular on administrative structures, on transparency or participatory elements in the global administrative procedure, on principles of reasoned decision-making, due process and on mechanisms of review. Thus, the field of GAL could encompass the totality of global rules governing administrative action by the global administrative bodies. (43) It would also study substantive law that defines the powers and lconstraints of regulatory bodies and the conditions under which particular state organs can interfere with concerned individual liberties. However, the field of GAL is not limited to the specific context of substantive rules, but rather the operation of existing or possible principles, procedural rules, review mechanisms and other mechanisms relating to accountability, participation, reasoned decision-making and assurance of legality in global governance. (44) At global level also there are distinctions among the various types of regulatory regimes. Where some global bodies provide a framework/policy for state action, the others establish guidelines addressed to domestic administrative agencies, and rest still impact directly upon national civil society actors. Further some of the governing regimes create their own implementation mechanisms, while others rely on national administration. To settle disputes, some regulatory regimes have established quasi-judicial forums. Thus, it is established that global organisations having own institutional identity, become much more than mere instruments of the member states; as they set their own norms to regulate their field of activity. It is claimed that they have emerged as genuine global public administrations. But critics often rebut this with the argument that there is absence of any proper legislative or judicial functions within the traditional conceptual structures of international law, and this alone gives rise to particular problems in terms of their legitimacy and accountability of global institutions. (45)

Issues with its formation: As above, nodoubt GAL is proposed to be a nascent structure at evolving state, with combination of international regulation and administrative law but at the global level, lack of uniformity, certainty and concreteness in the international law is the reason for dearth of just and fair administration of global regulatory bodies. Thus, unlike the domestic administrative law, where adherence to certain uniform or just principles, while taking administrative action by executives, can be discerned, in global regulatory body such certainty and uniformity is missing, which cause serious challange in development and emergence of proposal of GAL. Moreover scope/ jurisdiction and domain of such global bodies is not clear, which perplexed the scholars engeged in task of GAL. Now at this point the question in hand is to have clarity on the very definition of GAL.

Way Forwards: At this juncture the it is the need of the hour that this fast expanding global governing system shall be checked with proper mechanisms Thus, when under the neo-global administration the states and private entities are becoming administrative units of global institutions, necessity is felt to provide certain fundamental principles and procedures of administrative law, to ensure democratic values and natural justice principles in working of global administration. GAL on the lines of domestic Administrative is suggested as solution by many modern jurists and academicians as a check providing mechanism in context this global legal issue, so that, transparency, participation and accountability in global administrative working can be ensured.

Thus, the rising jurisdiction and influence of this global governance system, if not properly channelised and balances, can always have adversely affect upon vulnerable societies and weak states, including individuals or organisations.

Tools Used: This research work in this paper is based upon the doctrinal method of research. Different sources such as the books, articles, research papers, existing laws, judicial pronouncements, and the ICT platforms are explored.

Conclusion This research paper is focussed on discussing governing mechanisms in the working of emerging global organisations, which started regulating the entire global society directly and indirectly. In the modern era, ICT has introduced new dimensions in the connectivity of global society, which made every activity of human society global, to regulate which powerful and influential global level bodies emerged. These global entities created a new-global administration which started influencing entire global society. But at the same time lack of checks on global bodies, give scope for chances of abuse of authority by global governance at the cost of weaker society at the behest of strong societies as experienced. Many modern thinkers answer this problem with the term Global Administrative Law, however it is found that it is not easy to shape any such term easily as there are many jurisdictional, legal and political issues

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